
Topic: Thermal Comfort

Roots and mechanisms of thermal comfort expectations: from individuals' own background to adaptation and change

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Keywords: Thermal comfort, Indoor environmental quality, Expectation, Adaptation, Occupants

SUMMARY

The notion of thermal comfort has evolved through time, being the answer to various changes and influences in the built environment. Despite the common engineering definition, with measured ideal conditions matching with a state of neutrality, the concept is far more complex and requires a holistic multidisciplinary approach. Two main aspects are pivotal in the concept of comfort: expectation and adaptation, which depend themselves on several diversity-driving factors. However, their influence is nowadays generally neglected in buildings' design and operation, and standards.

The aim of this work is to understand and acknowledge, by means of a literature analysis, the different aspects that contribute to the inner workings of thermal comfort expectation and adaptation. The paper addresses all the different dynamics constituting the users' thermal background and their attitudes towards the indoor environment. Only an in deep understanding of the possible differences between different users' expectation and adaptation mechanisms will trigger an informed human-centric design process.

INTRODUCTION

Buildings are not built to create an enclosed space at constant temperature, but to provide comfortable conditions for its users. This does not imply that users are merely passively subjected to the Indoor Environmental Quality (IEQ) conditions, but as active beings they express their behaviour, attitudes, dynamics and controls over the environment [1]. Their main driver is achieving comfort and convenience, since people are interested in having access to services and not in energy consumptions per se [2]. Thus, it becomes pivotal to understand how users interact with the indoor environment and furthermore to address the diversities in these interactions to conceive energy efficient buildings whose performances are not jeopardized by unsatisfied users. With the term *comfort* it is commonly indicated a mind state where the subject expresses their level of satisfaction with the surrounding environment. However, understanding which factors impact that "mind state" is a very complex topic, covered by multiple different disciplines from

engineering, architecture and building physics, to social sciences, psychology, physiology, and anthropology. Evidence suggests that the notion of comfort is not one-dimensional, which would result into a very limited and narrow understanding, but it needs a more holistic approach to embrace all the different shades and natures. Due to this polyhedric nature, the very notion of comfort has evolved through time, being the answer to various changes and influences, i.e. cultural, social, technological and economic. According to Rybczynski [3], it was only in the XIX century that the term comfort was first used related to environmental comfort concerning heat, ventilation and light. Today, the word comfort is often associated with the thermal aspects, and as stated by ASHRAE [4] it is ‘the condition of mind that expresses satisfaction with the thermal environment’. In a very engineering perspective, comfort zones are strictly defined basing on ideal conditions to be measured and matches with a condition of neutrality. In other words, as stated in Brager and de Dear [5], the current ideal notion of comfort implies an absence of sensation, striving to create indoor environments that never vary over time or space, purposely creating a “sensationless, thermal Nirvana” [6]. Through time and history, this mindset has eventually led to the current common notion of indoor environment: very tight and static environments, where transition and stimuli are not admitted, with very narrow ranges of microclimatic parameters to be maintained equally for all the subjects. However, the situation is far more complex, and it is influenced by contextual boundaries and other socio-cultural influences. Indoor environments can be richer experiences than merely neutrality, with their own ability of providing valuable sensory stimulations to users. Going beyond this very limited concept means accounting for other variables impacting human experience, like climatic, architectural, psychological, physiological, behavioural, ecological, social, cultural, and etc..., which strongly influence humans’ own basic needs and personal attitudes towards the indoor environments.

According to thermal comfort evaluation approaches, two main models are internationally well known and accepted for assessing indoor conditions: the adaptive model and the PMV/PPD model. The latter, developed by P.O. Fanger [7], and based on the heat balance of the human body, has lately been often discussed since it implies a very static environment, which is made by narrow and constant conditions that do not reflect the variability in external climate, users’ perception, or adaptation mechanisms. On the other hand, the adaptive model [8] is based on the outdoor running mean temperature. It considers the users’ adaptability to various environments, accounts for transient and dynamic indoor conditions, and attempts to address diversities in users’ interactions. However, to certain extents, also this approach does not fully embrace the heterogeneity of the factors affecting users’ experience, being such variables not clearly acknowledge in the state of the art and very difficult to grasp by means of a specific indicator.

With this work, the authors aim to understand and acknowledge, by means of a literature analysis, all the different aspects which contribute to the inner workings of thermal comfort expectation and human adaptation processes. The final goal is to address all the different dynamics constituting the users’ thermal background and their attitudes towards the indoor environment, in order to propose an initial contribution to the thermal comfort theories and their application in real buildings.

METHODS

The work has been conducted by means of a literature review. As a first step, after a preliminary search on a restricted sample of documents, the authors have identified the most recurring

keywords so as to perform a more extensive research. The query has been implemented in the Scopus research tool [9] as TITLE-ABS-KEY (building* AND thermal AND comfort AND adapt* AND expectation*). First results output a list of 109 documents, to which 4 documents have been added as previously known and considered important by the authors. 3 documents were removed as duplicates. No preliminary blind filter has been adopted, but documents were manually screened according to the Title, reaching a final subset of 43 documents, including journal articles, conference papers and book chapters. 7 of them were not available for retrieval, thus achieving a final sample included in the review of 36 documents (Figure 1). In this work, among these 36 documents, after their reading, have been cited the ones significant for the aim of the work.

Figure 1. Workflow for the identification of the final set of documents included in the review. Elaborated from: Preferred Reporting Items for Systematic Reviews and Meta-Analyses (PRISMA) flow diagram, 2020 (PRISMA) [10]

RESULTS and DISCUSSION

As mentioned above, a user in the indoor environment has their own perception over it, and they strive to achieve comfort. However, as shown in Figure 2, the journey towards wellbeing is not an express train equal for all the subjects, as two main factors play a pivotal role: firstly expectation, also known in literature as preference or habituation, and adaptation. Thermal comfort is a subjective factor, which is closely associated with occupants' thermal expectations and capacity of adaptation [11].

In the dynamics of thermal comfort, user's expectation becomes a key element. Defined by Fanger himself as the "7th parameter in the heat balance model of thermal comfort" [12], it is a complex combination of many factors like user's climatic history, social understanding, cultural differences,

economic level, and others that will be addressed later in this work. For what concerns thermal comfort adaptation, according to Brager and de Dear [5], three main mechanisms play a key role: i) physiological acclimatization, namely changes in physiological responses, physiological set points and gains for controlling shivering, skin blood flow and sweating; ii) psychological adaptation, i.e. changes in perception and reaction to sensory information; iii) behavior adjustment, which is made by all the conscious actions taken by the user such as altering clothing, eating cold or hot food, using fans, and so on.

These two complex mechanisms have their roots in deeply-grounded histories of users, and their dynamics are affected by a multiplicity of factors related to different disciplines and sciences beyond the engineering and architecture limited sphere. Identifying all these aspects can enable a shift of paradigm into the design of buildings, in order to account for users' diversities and take a step aside from the ideal notion of comfort, re-enabling the concept of flexibility and transience, common in the vernacular or "non-pedigreed architectures", as a fine result of human intelligence applied to uniquely human modes of life [13].

Figure 2. Conceptualization of the user's interactions over the indoor environment with comfort as a key driver and expectation and adaptation as main actors in the process

1. The concept of expectation

Starting from the concept of expectation, this is highly influenced by so-called diversity-driving factors [14]. Such factors, according to those found in this review, could be clustered into different categories, namely climatic, socio-cultural, demographic and economical, ethnical and physical, and can either be associated strictly with an individual user or with more general features belonging to their Country of origin.

One main characteristic of expectation is that it has no symmetric dynamics. In fact, people living in higher IEQ indoor spaces become "fussy" to the thermal environment, having increasingly higher expectations and, furthermore, their thermoregulatory system begins to fail in its physiological reactions. It is consequently difficult to go back to lower IEQ conditions due to a developed excessive need of comfort and the so-called endowment effect [15].

- a. **Climatic** aspects. It is recurrent in various works that the long-term climatic history of a person influences their perception of the indoor thermal environment. According to Li et al. [11], climate is one of the factors affecting occupants' expectations towards thermal sensation, and it is not accounted in the common PMV-PPD model. This involves variations not only in the perceived neutral temperatures, but also in the interpretation of the ASHRAE scale categories and in personal judgements in the case of subjective surveys. The impact of long-term climatic

experience has been furtherly demonstrated in studies with group of people migrating between areas with different conditions [16] [12] [17] [18] [19]. Adaptation to new climatic conditions occurs over time however, according to Luo et al. [20], it may start from a few days or weeks after a users' move but will require months or years to be accomplished completely. In fact, human thermal adaptation requires quite a long time and it is rather complicated to estimate the exact amount. It involves different layers such as physiological acclimation, psychological adaptation, behavioral adjustment, and culture adaptation. The time constant of these layers may vary from days or weeks for behavior changes to seasons or years for the physiological layer, and even to decades or lifetime for culture adaptation.

- b. Socio-cultural** aspects. These factors also have a strong role in occupants' expectations, not only concerning the subject as an individual, but the context they are surrounded by. As extensively tackled in de Dear and Brager [5], convenience and leisure in the indoor environment are influenced by the concept of comfort as a socio-economic factor, and achieving a certain level of IEQ conditions has become an expression of the social status of an individual. Wellbeing is, in this way, an unfortunate expression of a material culture, expressed through social acceptability, societal differences, entitlement and living standard. This is also expressed in the work of Zhanga and de Dear [14] where the socio-economic status is enlisted in the diversity-driving factors impacting the thermal sensation. Moezzi, in his work [21], investigates the "right to consume" and sense of entitlement of occupants towards comfort, which quickly becomes nearly everything and drives users to expect too much and to place their general content in the acquisition of a very high IEQ standard. People are interested in having access to services and not in energy consumptions per se [2]. Services, obtained technologies, leisure and comfort are the face of a living standard and the expression of a person's achieved socio-economic status [22]. As expressed by Kahneman [15], people are eventually led by "the endowment effect" or "divestiture aversion", and place higher value on things merely because they currently own them or have done so in living, striving for maintaining the achieved leisure and status. On the contrary, people living in poor thermal environments for a long time may think it is their destiny, and they would judge a given poor environment as less unacceptable than those who are used to good thermal environments [17]. Their background has shaped their expectations and attitudes through time and space, changing their very own personal sensation and perception of the surrounding environment.
- c. Demographic and economic** aspects. These factors are the ones less related to one individual subject, but more widely linked to the Country in which they live in. The economical level of a region, in fact, has a strong effect on the penetration of technologies in peoples' homes, and thus in the penetration of such standards in their everyday expectations. A strong example in this direction, connected both to social and economic aspects, is the case of mechanical heating or cooling over passive strategies occurred in the United States during the 50s. Air conditioning (AC) has had significant positive impacts on society, with also enormous historical and cultural effects on peoples' attitudes about comfort, the way in which we design and inhabit buildings, and even ways in which we interact as a society. However, AC soon became the expression of cultural and societal changes, including the role of family, gender, and social class. It embodied a socio-economic status, leading to an addiction and treated as an entitlement for social acceptability. It was the symbol of a material culture and economic competition of the entire Country and, initially driven by cultural and social issues, AC evolved into a physiological addiction, where 'air-conditioning rapidly teaches the body to hate the heat' [6], and changed

people's perception and expectations and their response to outdoor climate. Nowadays, the same process is happening in the developing countries, where AC and its implementation is a hint of the economic status of the Country and of its inhabitants [23]. According to Li et al. [11], some demographic and contextual factors, such as educational background, ethnicity, body mass and social status, may influence thermal sensation. Also in Luo et al. [20], cultural differences and economical level have an effect on the indoor climate experience, where modernization over time changes the social understanding of comfort and makes it malleable. The economic level of a specific region, its policies and industry spin play a key role especially in the adoption of a certain technology. Consequently, the level of technologies available and their level of use impact the expectation of users in terms of comfort, being their adaptation background highly influenced and determined by the level of convenience they are used to. A technology can be the expression of technological abundance and of economic thrive of a nation, but silently can change peoples' level of comfort and convenience and reinforce their addiction to newly human-self-created needs. In addition to this, the spread of technologies has often political and policy consequences [5], as these large populations use their voices and votes to elect representatives who will vote in matter of energy, incentives or restrictions, or other policy options that would inhibit their energy access.

- d. **Ethnical, physical and physiological** aspects. As explained in Li et al. [11], human genome imparted by natural selection is strongly correlated with climatic variables: people exposed for a long time to a certain climatic context may have different tolerance for temperature and humidity levels. In addition to this, other factors including ethnicity and body mass are known to play a role in the thermal sensation. Ethnographic factors are also mentioned by Moezzi [21]. Beside this, extensive research has been conducted on the role of gender and age towards comfort expectations.

For what concerns age, current thermal comfort models seem to be not sufficiently accurate to be used for elder people, since age plays an effect on the physiology of the human body and adults adaptation or options of personal control among older people may be limited in comparison with young adults. Aged persons show impaired thermoregulatory control and may require a more intense thermal stimulus to elicit the appropriate behavioral responses in the home. It is also possible that such stimuli will result in a greater heat flow, elevating the risk of dysthermia in the aged [24]. In Indraganti and Rao [25] a significant but poor correlation was observed between age and 'thermal sensation' and 'overall comfort'. In addition, 'thermal non-acceptance' was lower in older subjects. Moreover, energy access and energy poverty, connected with financial limitations, are more likely to happen with elder people, and this may lead to suboptimal living conditions and may lead to morbidity and mortality [26] [27]. On the other side, children have themselves a different physiological, psychological and behavioral response to stimuli than adults. For example, in Yun et al. [28] it has been shown that children were more sensitive to changes in their metabolism than adults, and their preferred temperature was lower than that predicted by the PMV and the Adaptive Models. The results in Teli et al. [29] suggest that children have a different thermal perception than adults. According to the authors, pupils' overall comfort is not always related to their thermal state, i.e. some may feel hot but state that they are feeling comfortable. Children appear to have a higher metabolic rate per kg body weight and seem to experience, due to their daily schedule, a variation of activity levels and a strong relationship with the outdoor climate different to adult office activities. In

addition, kids take limited adaptive action with regards to clothing during the day, but this highly depends on the socio-cultural norms and school regulations.

On the side of gender implications, the review conducted by Karjalainen [30] shows that a growing number of studies have found significant differences in thermal comfort between the genders. More than half of the laboratory and field studies have found that females express more dissatisfaction than males in the same thermal environments and females seem to be more sensitive than males to a deviation from an optimal temperature and express more dissatisfaction, especially in cooler conditions.

An important mention is necessary when it comes to people with disabilities, who may have a different perception and use of the surrounding environment. In fact, they could have an impaired physiological response, as well as some limitations for what concerns behavioral and adaptation mechanisms. This can have a strong impact on all the comfort areas, depending on the type and level of disability. For example, for what concerns thermal comfort, people with physical disabilities have a different activity level and metabolic rate, do have less opportunity of adaptation by movement or clothing and, if space and appliances are not properly design, they can also experience difficulties in the management of systems and operation. According to Parsons [31], people with disabilities have different thermal requirements due to mobility, postural and anthropometric differences as well as effects on thermoregulatory responses caused by the disability itself (blood flow, sweating, shivering, etc.) or methods to cope with the disability such as the use of drugs. Moreover, it seems that many people with physical disabilities were affected both physically and mentally when they are in a state of thermal discomfort [32]. Also in this case, as for elder occupants, financial limitations can also be the cause of suboptimal living conditions.

2. The concept of adaptation

Adaptation is the process by which the user adapts in the indoor environment in order to achieve comfort, responding to a particular stimulus by putting into effect the three main thermal adaption mechanisms cited above [5]. However, the response made by an individual to any particular stimulus will strongly depend upon contextual factors. In fact, the extent to which an individual can change his clothing, the number and typology of activities, and the use of environmental controls, depend on social limits, pressures, circumstances, and social constraints that consist in the limits of the obtained control [33]. Thus, a self-regulating control system works to ensure thermal comfort, and it will in any case strive towards its optimum. The problem is to provide to each individual the right circumstances in which this mechanism can easily take place. For this reason, it becomes so important to investigate these circumstances and constraints which affect occupants' capacity to self-regulate by adaptation mechanisms.

a. Environmental and contextual factors. According to the user-centered theories for the built environment, two different positions can be identified: i) an environmental determinism, which assumes that the environment causes the users' behavior; ii) a social constructivism, where the human attitudes are determined by the social context. The first one, favored for its immediate applicability, has revealed to minimize and oversimplify all the possible variables that influence the human behavior, whereas human experience is highly influenced also by social norms, interactions and constructions. For these reasons, according to Vischer [34], a user-centered theory is more located in between these two extremes: subjects' behavior is influenced by the

environment but not determined by it, while being affected by other aspects like feelings, intentions, attitudes, expectations and social context. Cultural and social variables include a very wide range of aspects and topics, from a household level to a community one, with a perspective that often goes beyond the individual attitudes. According to Watson et al. [35], group mechanisms include: i) organizational cultures, referring to organizational or institutional social order; ii) management strategies, as the processes that control individual users and user groups; iii) social norms and practices, referring to the tacit knowledge and related behavior patterns of individual users.

- b. Building typology.** Among the different factors affecting adaptation, the building type and its systems clearly are the main ones. In fact, comparing the potential of adaptation in users' own home versus in their office building, it is evident that this involves the presence of other people in the same space, shared dynamics, social conventions (e.g. clothing requirements) and shared controls. In this perspective, the so-called "adaptation by coexistence" of the work of Marín-Restrepo et al. [36] perfectly embraces the concept. In shared spaces, adaptive actions can be limited by a coexistence factor, which has an impact on thermal expectations. The needs and expectations of people are specific, but the actions comfort-driven are subjected to constraints on the range of actions that people can perform in order to adapt the environment or adapt themselves to it, whether by physical, social or other factors. Social concerns play an important role in the way that occupants interact with a building and adapt themselves to its conditions, and behavior is limited by social influences, since undertaking an adaptive action may bother other occupants.
- c. Ventilation mode.** On the side of technical solutions and operation strategies, some literature works have in particular highlighted the difference between Naturally and Mechanically ventilated buildings. In a massive study conducted by de Dear and Brager [37], the ASHARE Global Thermal Comfort database was analyzed to draw findings about users' thermal preferences in the two types of ventilated indoor spaces. For what concerns mechanically ventilated buildings, occupants revealed to have become finely adapted to the narrow and constant conditions typically provided by the mechanical system. They used to become quickly uncomfortable if conditions deviated from the narrow set points. On the contrary, occupants of naturally ventilated buildings were adapting behaviorally and psychologically to the varied indoor climates driven by external weather and season cycles.
- d. Personal control** is also a key factor, since it allows to increase the inhomogeneity of the thermal environment, expanding the temperature control range, while increasing the subjective satisfaction rate [38]. In the study conducted by Brager et al. [39] in a naturally ventilated office building, it was demonstrated how occupants with more opportunities to operate windows voted thermal sensation closer to neutral than those who had less power over control. According to Zhou et al. [40], thermal comfort improvements can happen merely due to psychological factors. In this direction, the study conducted by Luo et al. [12], has shown how an improvement of comfort is not only due to merely physical conditions, but the psychological effects play a key role in the mechanisms of adaptation. Subjects' perceived ability to control over thermal environment improves their thermal comfort perception, and this improvement is merely due to a psychological influence. The users' thermal discomforts can be reduced through even a very slight improvement of the thermal conditions implemented via personal controls. Thus, it is recommended that occupants are provided with sufficient opportunities to control their thermal environments.

- e. **Physical characteristics and special needs.** Of course, adaptation, similarly to expectation, depends also on users' personal features: people with reduced mobility potential, like disabled people or elders, can struggle to adapt to the environment, both physiologically and behaviorally, and their reduced activity level impacts their thermal sensation and capacity of increasing the metabolic activity.

CONCLUSIONS

In this paper, the authors propose a first contribution for accounting for diversity factors in users' expectation and adaptation mechanisms towards thermal comfort. In fact, nowadays diversity is neither accounted into building design and operation, nor foremost into standard and guidelines. However, expectation plays a pivotal role into affecting the occupants' perception of the indoor environment, as well as adaptation is key in the process of achieving comfort.

These two aspects have one thing in common: both are influenced and shaped by a variety of other features, related to the individual user but also to a wider contextual sphere, as highlighted in the different works cited in this review.

Further work is still clearly needed. From the side of this specific work, this literature review can be extended and achieve a better definition of the different aspects, in order to provide ready-to-use outputs to be implemented in the common practice. From a more general point of view of research, there is still a huge potential of analysis with the conduction of further extensive research on the different aspects involved in the process of thermal comfort. Post Occupancy Evaluation (POE) campaigns, for example, is for sure a useful tool for addressing diversities in expectation and adaptation processes among different users. Questionnaires, which implement specific questions to address users' characteristics and habits, can be administrated along with monitoring campaigns in different geographical location to identify how the various factors influence the human thermal comfort, perception, and sensation. Differences can be addressed as characterized by all the aspects analyzed in this work, from climatic, to cultural, social, historical, anthropological, demographical, economic, and physical, to provide new input to standards toward an indoor environment meant to welcome user's specificities while promoting energy efficiency.

ACKNOWLEDGEMENT

This work has been conducted within the EU H2020 Cultural-E project funded from the European Union's Horizon 2020 research and innovation programme under grant agreement N. 870072.

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